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TEMPLATE FORM ON FACULTY FULL-BLOWN PROPOSAL AND FINAL IMRAD MANUSCRIPT

Title:

Converting Biological Resources into Herbal-Based Ointment for Topical Application:
Formulation and Efficacy Evaluation

Proponents

Lead Researcher Mrs. Cathelyn C. Mariano, LPT, MA
Primary Collaborator Mrs. Ma. Shiela M. Ramos, RMT
Research Assistant Gabrielle Christoph Eraña, RPH
External Collaborators BLGU (Sitio Masina, Baretbet, Bagabag, NV)

Abstract

The use of biological resources such as plant extracts for therapeutic purposes is increasingly popular, even in communities with access to modern medicine, due to their significant healing potential and low side effects. Antimicrobial ointments are vital in healthcare for treating bacterial infections, wound healing, and preventing secondary infections. This study aimed to formulate and evaluate a topical antimicrobial ointment using ethanolic leaf extracts of *Sandoricum koetjape* (*Santol*) and *Cassia alata* (*Andadasi/Acapulco*) against clinically relevant skin pathogens. This research focused on the antimicrobial potency, optimizing extract concentration, and evaluating the physical and safety characteristics of the final formulation. Antimicrobial activity was tested against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Candida albicans* using crude extract concentrations of 250, 500, and 750 mg/mL. Results revealed that *Santol* extract showed the most significant inhibition (active) against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, while *Cassia alata* extract exhibited strong antifungal activity (very active) against *Candida albicans*. Both extracts demonstrated moderate to strong activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*. Topical ointments were then formulated using the most effective extract concentration (750 mg/mL). The resulting products displayed desirable physical properties such as smooth semi-solid consistency, natural herbal scent, skin-compatible pH (5.1–6.6), and excellent spreadability. Safety assessment through patch and scratch tests confirmed the absence of edema, indicating non-irritating and well-tolerated formulations. Overall, result supports the potential of *santol* and *andadasi* as sources of natural antimicrobial agents in topical preparations. Additionally, a formulation guide was developed to enable home-based preparation of ointments using plant-derived ingredients. For future utilization, the formulation guide will be disseminated to communities and train residents, enabling reproducibility and potential scale-up for broader use in community or clinical settings.

Keywords: antimicrobial activity, formulation guide, non-irritancy test, scratch-patch test, zone of inhibition

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I. Introduction

Throughout history, societies across the globe have discovered ways to combat illness and preserve the healing advantages of plants. These available and culturally important traditional medicines form the basis of an accessible and affordable health care regime and are an essential source of livelihood for indigenous and rural populations (Awoyemi et al., 2012). Traditional medicine (TM), as defined by the World Health Organization, is the sum total of the knowledge, skills, and practices based on the theories, beliefs, and experiences indigenous to different cultures, whether explicable or not, used in the maintenance of health as well as in the prevention, diagnosis, improvement, or treatment of physical and mental illness. These experiences and knowledge are handed down from generation to generation. Although modern medicine is widely spread, traditional medicine still exists and widely used in the Philippines. People are now more prepared to look for alternative approaches to maintain their health. According to Mr. Albert M.G. Garcia, President of the Chamber of Herbal Industries of the Philippines, Inc., one of the biggest global trends in the past years has been the growing interest in health and well-being. It has become increasingly important to consumers to improve both their own health and the environment they live in. Natural and organic household and home care products are becoming more in demand by consumers who are interested in their health and well-being, inducing more job opportunities in the sector (<https://industry.gov.ph/industry/natural-health-products/>).

Indigenous medicinal plants in the Philippines are investigated either for the in vivo and vitro pharmacological properties of any of their extracts or for the isolation of bioactive secondary metabolites. Due to technological advancement, some medicinal plants are being processed and served as home remedies and being transformed as tablets, capsules, creams, and ointments for commercialization, where locals can cultivate them in their backyard. These commercialized medicinal plants are effective; however, consumers may wonder about the processing of the product that may or may not contain impurities and contamination compared to a freshly picked medicinal plant (Mukherjee, 2019). Since plants have been the source of a large percentage of prescription drugs, it is very important that the antimicrobial properties of medicinal plants be investigated because these plants could be a resource for new and alternative treatment for some common infectious diseases.

In the study of *Mariano, et al., (2023)* on the ethnobotanical documentation and diversity assessment of medicinal flora used by local inhabitants in Sitio Masina, Bagabag, Nueva Vizcaya, the local inhabitants mentioned that skin rashes, insect bites, itchiness, wounds and other skin related infections are very common health condition both for children and adult in their community. This is probably due to the demographic location of the Sitio. It is mountainous and abounds with water resources such as rivers, and natural springs, and waterfalls. Most of the inhabitants live near/on mountains, plains, and farmlands area leading a traditional way of life.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), skin disease is one of the top 50 causes of deaths in the Philippines in 2018. Examples of skin diseases prevalent in the country are the following: *pyoderma*, a bacterial skin inflammation encountered most frequently in tropical places where heat and humidity further contributes to infection growth; *eczema*, a common skin problem which causes red, itchy and scaly skin. In severe cases, the skin may even weep or bleed; *scabies*, an infectious skin condition which can spread from person to person through close physical contact, the infection is caused by mites burrowed beneath the skin which results in itchiness and the occurrence of pimple-like rashes.

Skin diseases may be treated through the use of topical creams, ointments, oral medications, and through injections, depending on the patient's condition. Some patients may need to be admitted in hospitals which may lead to costly hospital fees (DOST-PCHRD).

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During the SHNS Medical Mission conducted within Sitio Masina, Baretbet, Bagabag, Nueva Vizcaya, year 2022 and held at Tonus Gymnasium in 2023, some adults were asking medicines for the treatment of skin allergies, wounds and itchiness.

Additionally, the ethnobotanical documentation conducted by Mariano, Villanueva, Barroga and Dinamling in 2022 at Sitio Masina, revealed that many of the residents tend to seek treatment from folkloric practices. Among the plants being identified and utilized for the treatment and cure of skin related disease are acapulco, alugbati and santol leaves. Furthermore, in 2023, Mariano et al., disseminated and distributed a catalogue containing the usage of the medicinal plants commonly used by the local residents. Since, they are one of the adopted communities of SMU, they have been very vocal in expressing their needs, one mentioned, "*masurwan kami kuma nga maka-aramid ti agas para iti kudil, lalo para kadagiti ubbing*"; in groups, they said "*wen kuma, tay kaya mi laeng nga aramiden ditoy ayan mi*".

Natural medicines are relatively cheaper, they have lesser side effects, better patient tolerance, and are acceptable due to a long history of use. The essential metabolites derived from medicinal plants are potential sources of antimicrobial agents against multiple-drug resistant (MDR) bacteria.

This present research offers then a promising avenue for the formulation of alternative, safe, efficient, and cost-effective home-based antimicrobial ointment which is conducive to topical application and patient compliance. This will contribute to the development of alternative therapies using biological-natural sources, readily available ingredients and can simply be made by the residents in their own houses.

Prevalence of Specific Skin Conditions in the Philippines

The tropical climate of the Philippines, characterized by high temperatures and humidity, can create conditions favorable for the growth and spread of various pathogens that cause skin infections, such as bacteria, fungi, and viruses. Certain skin conditions, such as fungal infections like tinea (ringworm) or bacterial infections like impetigo, may be more prevalent in the Philippines due to cultural practices, lifestyle factors, or environmental conditions. According to the latest WHO data published in 2020 Skin Disease Deaths in Philippines reached 4,229 or 0.63% of total deaths. The age adjusted Death Rate is 6.88 per 100,000 of population ranks Philippines number 10 in the world (<https://www.worldlifeexpectancy.com/philippines-skin-disease>).

The *amihan season*, or northeast monsoon season, when the prevailing temperature is much lower, brings with it a higher risk of contracting several skin ailments. The said season commonly starts in October and ends in March each year in the Philippines. Dr. Marjorie Lalaine Salazar, a skin health and aesthetic physician, of the Philippine Association of Primary Skin Health Physicians, Inc. (PAPSHPI), warned that the *amihan* season can cause various skin problems, such as xerosis (dry skin), eczema (a skin condition that causes itchy, dry, and reddish lesions), and flare-ups of psoriasis (a chronic skin disease that brings about red and scaly patches on the body). As to the prevention of these skin problems, Dr. Salazar recommended the use of coconut oil, an abundant natural resource in the Philippines (<https://thefilipinodoctor.com/article/watch-out-for-skin-problems-during-the-amihan-season-2>).

Topical Antimicrobials

Antimicrobials have been present in nature for much longer than their use by humans. The study of interactions between different microorganisms, whether prokaryotes or eukaryotes, is an important source of new antimicrobial discovery (Molloy & Hertweck, 2017). Ecological knowledge of antimicrobial production conditions, functions and roles in an ecosystem is necessary for the

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discovery of new antimicrobials and their safe and effective use. Antimicrobials can kill microorganisms and/or prevent their growth by targeting key steps in cellular metabolism such as the synthesis of biological macromolecules, the activity of cellular enzymes, or cellular structures such as the cell wall, and cell membranes (Pursell, 2020; Romani, et al., 2022).

According to Dr. Nazneen Memon, a Bachelor of Homeopathic Medicine and Surgery certified by the Maharashtra University of Health Sciences, topical antimicrobials are medications applied directly to the skin to treat bacterial infections and reduce symptoms like redness, swelling, and itching. They play a key role in preventing and treating superficial bacterial infections, often used as first aid for minor wounds and abrasions. These agents inhibit microbial growth and have bactericidal effects, killing bacteria while minimizing harm to normal skin flora. They are available in various forms such as creams, ointments, lotions, scrubs, and swabs, and are characterized by fast, prolonged antibacterial action with low toxicity (https://www.rxlist.com/how_do_topical_antimicrobials_work/drug-class.htm).

In the study of Pallab, et al., (2019), they revealed that topically applied antibacterial agents are widely used. Topical application has many potential advantages over systemic therapy that includes high and sustained concentrations of drug directly at the infected site, low quantity of antibiotic needed, better compliance, fewer systemic side effects and potentially less chance of antimicrobial resistance.

A variety of topical antibiotics are commercially available such as *bacitracin*, *mupirocin*, *gramicidin*, *fusidic acid* and *gentamycin*. *Trimycin* is a topical antibacterial ointment containing bacitracin, polymyxin B Sulfate and neomycin. These agents are used for the prevention or treatment of superficial skin infections caused by susceptible bacteria. (<https://www.unilab.com.ph/products/trimycin>).

Botanicals or plant-derived natural products are also used as topical antibacterial agents. They usually contain essential oils, oleoresins, and other components used as medicine or for other purposes. They are relatively nontoxic, and more susceptible to bacterial resistance.

Biological Activities of the Identified Plant Samples

Cassia alata (Acapulco)

Cassia alata, locally known in Tagalog as *andadasi* and *acapulco* or *ringworm bush* in English, is an erect, shrubby legume with dark green compound leaves that grows wild in the tropical climate of the Philippines and an affordable locally sourced of herbal medicine. The plant is highly valued in many areas of the tropics for its medicinal virtues. It is commonly gathered from the wild, mainly for medicinal use but also as a food and source of materials. It is often cultivated for medicinal purposes, and also as an ornamental plant in tropical to warm temperate areas (Whistler, 2000). Agri Digitale (2021), confirmed that ethanol extract and water extract got by boiling the *C. alata* leaves in water has amazing anti-fungal properties and anti-microbial properties making them very effective for treating skin diseases. It is very effective against ringworm as it has anti dermatophyte properties which are the main causes of ringworm. In addition, the study of Fatmawati, et al., (2020) disclosed that *C. alata* has been reported to have potential anti allergic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anticancer, antidiabetic, and antifungal properties.

In the Philippines, its leaves have been traditionally used to treat fungal skin infections such as ringworms, scabies, and eczema. Results of several clinical trials prove that it is as effective as synthetic antifungal agents in the treatment of superficial skin infections (Institute of Herbal Medicine National Institute of Health, University of the Philippines-Manila). Because of acapulco's

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anti-fungal properties, it is a common ingredient in soaps, shampoos, and lotions in the Philippines (<http://www.medicalhealthguide.com/articles/akapulko1.htm>).

Sandoricum koetjape (santol)

Santol, also known as *cotton fruit*, is a tree growing up to 20 meters high, with softly hairy young branches and leaves. It is well-known in the Philippines and is located in almost all provinces. Throughout settled areas in the Philippines, santol tree are planted or semi-cultivated, and abundant in secondary forests). Santol offers a variety of health benefits and has been used by locals for different treatments. Indigenous groups (IG) in Ifugao and Nueva Vizcaya used santol to treat diarrhea while IG in Region II, used the fruit for fever and diarrhea, and they also placed santol bark inside the casket as material for embalming. On the other hand, *Ayta* people of Porac, Pampanga apply mashed fresh leaves throughout the body as repellent against hematophagous insects. Its bitter roots, bruised with vinegar and water, is used for diarrhea and dysentery (Stuart, 2021). Based on the study of Bajon et al., (2019), santol leaves is used to cure diarrhea, fever, and to treat ringworm and armyworm. Fresh santol leaves applied to the skin are sudorific. In addition, Obico & Ragragio (2014), confirmed that santol leaves are used for skin infections and rashes.

In Sito Masina, *andadasi*, and *santol* leaves have been traditionally used for the treatment of insect bites, ringworm, wounds, allergies, itchiness and as a laxative, hypertension, decoction of the leaves are used for cough and to get rid of intestinal worms. The residents claimed the wonderful medicinal properties of these plants.

Therefore, these studies highlight the biological activities of these plants which has been shown to have pharmacological properties against selected diseases.

Formulation of ointment

The development of herbal-based antimicrobial ointments presents a promising strategy for combating microbial infections, particularly those affecting the skin. These ointments offer targeted, localized treatment, reducing the risk of systemic side effects often associated with oral antibiotics while also promoting wound healing. Herbal extracts are rich in diverse bioactive compounds that can work synergistically to enhance antimicrobial effectiveness and potentially reduce the risk of resistance development. Topical formulations serve three primary functions: they protect the injured area from environmental exposure to facilitate skin regeneration; they hydrate the skin or provide an emollient effect; and they deliver active compounds either for local therapeutic action or, in some cases, for systemic absorption (<https://pharmacylibrary.com/doi/10.21019/9781582123578.ch21>).

Of all skin products, ointments contain the most oil. They stay on top of the skin rather than being absorbed right away, as a result, it offers more protection against moisture loss and the elements, like cold or dry air. Common ingredients found in ointments include mineral oil and petroleum (<https://www.healthline.com/health/ointment-vs-cream>).

The precise composition and ratio of ingredients in an ointment formulation are determined by several factors, including the intended properties of the product such as texture, absorption rate, and ingredient compatibility as well as stability requirements and regulatory considerations. Conducting stability testing is crucial to confirm the formulation's safety, effectiveness, and long-term integrity. Moreover, all formulations must adhere to relevant pharmaceutical regulations and guidelines (Gupta & Jain, 2018).

In this context, the formulation and evaluation of an herbal-based antimicrobial ointment for topical application represent a crucial area of research. By leveraging the natural antimicrobial properties of *Acapulco* and *Santol* leaves, there is potential to create an effective alternative to

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conventional antibiotic treatments. However, the successful development of such ointment requires comprehensive evaluation of its physicochemical characteristics, antimicrobial activity, and safety profile.

This research is strongly aligned with SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being) and also supports SDGs 1 (No Poverty), 4 (Quality Education), 11 (Sustainable Communities), 12 (Responsible Consumption, and 15 (Life on Land). This work focus on traditional medicine, indigenous knowledge, and community empowerment embodies a holistic, multi-SDG approach to sustainable and equitable development.

Conceptual and Analytical Framework

One of SMU's Research and Development objective is to produce research products or outcomes that can be readily utilized for relevant community extension services and institutional needs and concerns. This research is anchored with *The Bahay Kubo Framework for Research Agenda Setting of SMU's Project WEALTH VERSION 2.0 13-Point Agenda*, specifically on Wellness and Health areas. It is also in-line with the DOH-DOST National Unified Health Research Agenda (NUHRA) which involves the development of standardized herbal drugs found from local terrestrial sources up to the clinical stage.

Natural medicines are cost-effective, exhibit fewer side effects, and are generally better tolerated by patients due to their long history of use. Medicinal plants serve as a valuable source of essential metabolites, which hold promise as antimicrobial agents against multidrug-resistant (MDR) bacteria. While many antimicrobial agents are derived from microorganisms, chemotherapeutic compounds often originate from plants. Consequently, there is a growing interest in developing alternative therapies using biological resources readily available within local communities.

This research was guided by the research paradigm presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1
Research Paradigm

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The conceptual framework for this study was grounded in the notion that natural medicines offered several advantages, including lower costs, fewer side effects, and better patient tolerance, largely due to their extensive historical use.

This study involved the preparation of ethanolic extracts from *Cassia alata* (*Acapulco*) and *Sandoricum koetjape* (*santol*) at different concentrations of 250, 500 and 750 mg/ml respectively. These concentrations were used to determine the most effective levels for inhibiting microbial growth. The efficacy of each concentration was assessed by comparing the zones of inhibition on *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *C. albicans*. An ointment base, such as coconut oil or petroleum jelly, was prepared, and ointments were formulated by incorporating the most effective concentrations for each plant sample. Following formulation, the ointments underwent physicochemical evaluation, focusing on characteristics like color, odor, pH, viscosity, spreadability, stability, and irritancy. Safety for topical application was verified through scratch and patch tests using animal model. The ultimate goal of this research was to develop a home-based antimicrobial ointment. Additionally, a formulation guide was created, detailing the necessary materials, procedures, and applications.

For future utilization and dissemination, a training program will be conducted to educate barangay officials and residents on formulating their own antimicrobial ointments by utilizing known medicinal plants that are found in their community. This initiative aims to empower local communities by providing them with the skills and knowledge needed to produce these essential products independently. By doing so, it will address the challenges posed by geographical distance and financial constraints that often hinder access to pharmacies and clinics. This approach not only enhanced self-sufficiency but also promotes health equity within the community.

Statement of the Objectives

Generally, this study aimed to formulate and evaluate a topical antimicrobial ointment derived from ethanolic leaf extracts of *Sandoricum koetjape* (*santol*), and *Cassia alata* (*andadasi/acapulco*) targeting clinically relevant pathogens. It was conducted from February-March, 2025.

The following are the specific objectives:

1. Determine the antimicrobial efficacy of *santol* and *andadasi/acapulco*, leaf extracts against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Candida albicans*, with quantitative comparisons across concentrations (250, 500 and 750 mg/mL).
2. Formulate an antimicrobial ointment by integrating the most effective leaf extracts concentration.
3. Evaluate the physical characteristics of the formulated antimicrobial ointment, including *visual homogeneity*, spreadability, and pH.
4. Assess the safety profile of the formulated antimicrobial ointment through non-irritancy test and scratch and patch test.
5. Develop a formulation guide featuring step-by-step protocols for extract preparation, ointment formulation and safety guidelines for storage and application.

II. Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-experimental design to assess the antimicrobial properties of leaf extracts from the *santol* and *andadasi* plants. Various concentrations of these extracts were prepared for testing. Antimicrobial assays were conducted to assess the efficacy of the formulated

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ointment against clinically significant bacterial and fungal strains. Additionally, the safety profile of the ointment for topical application was evaluated through scratch and patch tests. To ensure reliability, three replicates were conducted for measuring the zones of inhibition of the test organisms. Furthermore, a detailed assessment of the physical characteristics of the formulated ointment was documented.

Study Site and Sample Collection

The collection of the plant samples was conducted at Sitio Masina, Baretbet, Bagabag, Nueva Vizcaya. The area was mountainous and abounded with water resources such as rivers, natural springs, and waterfalls. Most of the inhabitants lived near the mountains, plains, and farmlands, leading a traditional way of life. The area has a high number of endemic species, and the social importance of the medicinal plants in the community is essential for public health and the conservation of traditional knowledge. The experimentation and formulation of the antimicrobial ointment was conducted at the SMU Center for Natural Sciences (CNS) Research Laboratory, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya.

Organisms Utilized in the Study

Plant Samples

Two plant samples such as santol (*Sandoricum koetjape*) and andadasi (*Cassia alata*) were used in the formulation of a topical ointment. These plants were specifically requested by the local residents of Sitio Masina to be evaluated for their pharmacological properties. According to the ethnobotanical assessment of medicinal plants conducted in Sitio Masina by Mariano et al. (2023), the residents had long utilized these plants for the treatment of skin allergies, wounds, and itchiness.

Animal Specimen

One albino rat, obtained from a veterinary clinic in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, was used for the scratch and patch test.

Test Organisms

Staphylococcus aureus and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were the commonly occurring gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria that caused skin infections, along with the fungus *Candida albicans*, which were chosen for the study. These microorganisms were obtained from the SMU-CNS Research Laboratory and were properly identified by Registered Medical Technologists in the SMU Medical Technology Department.

Data Gathering Procedure

Preparation of the Crude Extracts

The leaves of the plant samples were thoroughly washed and oven-dried until they became completely brown and crispy. They were then pulverized using a blender to reduce their size (Guevarra et al., 2015). The pulverized leaves underwent maceration with a sufficient amount of 95% ethanol for 24 hours. The mixture was filtered using cheesecloth to obtain the extracts. After the extraction, the solvent was evaporated using a rotary evaporator at 40°C to yield the crude extract. Dilution followed using 95% ethanol as the diluent. The various dilutions included 50 mg of crude extract per mL of 95% ethanol, as well as concentrations of 250, 500 and 750 mg/mL. These concentrations were used for the antimicrobial assay.

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Antimicrobial Assay of the Plant Extracts

Microbiological media, including Mueller Hinton Agar and Nutrient Broth, were prepared by the CNS Laboratory staff, along with other chemicals and standard control drugs. There were three plate replicates for each test organism. The procedure was based on Guevarra et al. (2015), with slight modifications based on the CNS protocols and the availability of media and reagents. The antimicrobial assay was conducted by the CNS Laboratory assistant and was analyzed by the primary collaborator of this research, an expert and Registered Medical Technologist.

The antibacterial activity of the ethanolic extracts of the leaves of *acapulco*, and *santol* at concentrations of 250 mg/mL, 500 mg/mL, and 750 mg/mL was determined using the paper disc method. Molten Mueller Hinton agar, stabilized at 45 °C, was seeded with 0.1 mL of a 24-hour broth culture of the test organisms (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*), containing approximately 10^8 cfu/mL, in sterile Petri dishes and allowed to set. Sterile paper discs were impregnated with the ethanolic extracts of the leaves of *acapulco*, and *santol* at the specified concentrations. These discs were then placed onto the surface of the agar plates. The plates were pre-incubated for 1 hour at room temperature to allow for diffusion of the extracts, followed by incubation for 24 hours. After incubation, the zones of inhibition surrounding each paper disc were measured (mean, n=2). The microbial response to the extracts was evaluated based on the diameter of the zones of inhibition. The most effective concentration for each plant sample was subsequently used in the formulation of the *acapulco*, and *santol* antimicrobial ointment.

The antifungal activity of the ethanolic extracts of the leaves of *acapulco*, and *santol* at concentrations of 250 mg/mL, 500 mg/mL, and 750 mg/mL was determined against *Candida albicans* using the paper disc method. Sabouraud dextrose agar plates were prepared, and 100 μ L of a fungal suspension containing 10^5 CFU/mL was spread across the agar plates using a sterile cotton swab. After allowing the plates to dry, sterile paper discs were impregnated with the ethanolic extracts at the specified concentrations and placed onto the surface of the agar plates. The plates were then incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. Following the incubation period, the zones of inhibition surrounding each paper disc were measured using a Vernier caliper (Bharat et al., 2023). The effectiveness of the extracts was evaluated based on the diameter of the zones of inhibition.

The results were compared to positive controls such as clindamycin for *S. aureus*; ciprofloxacin for *P. aeruginosa* and fluconazole for *C. albicans*.

Formulation of Topical Acapulco, and Santol Ointment

Based on the antimicrobial results, only the extracts from *acapulco* and *santol* leaves were used to formulate the ointment.

The procedure was based on the protocol of Bharat et al. (2023), with slight modifications made under the supervision of a Registered Pharmacist. The formulation and evaluation of the topical ointment were carried out by a Registered Pharmacist. There were two formulations per plant extract, coded as AC1-AC2, and S1-S3, with specific concentration of coconut oil. The *acapulco*, and *santol* extracts (100 mg) were incorporated into each formulation. The ointments were prepared using the fusion method, in which the lipid components (coconut oil) was heated separately until completely melted. The *acapulco*, and *santol* extracts were then dispersed into the molten lipid mixture, and the resulting blend was cooled to room temperature to form the final ointment.

Physical Characteristic Evaluation of the Formulated Ointment

The physical characteristics of the formulated ointment were evaluated to ensure its quality, stability, and suitability for topical application. Standard evaluation methods are based on guidelines from pharmacopeias and formulation science. The key parameters include:

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Visual homogeneity

Physical parameters like color, odor and consistency were examined by visual examination.

pH

An electronic PH meter was used to measure the pH of the produced herbal ointment. A 100ml of distilled water was used to make the ointment solution, which was then left to sit for two hours. The solution's pH was measured three times, with the average value being computed.

Spreadability was determine how easily the ointment spreads on the skin.

Non irritancy Test

The prepared herbal ointment was applied to human skin and observed for its effects.

Scratch and Patch Test

The protocol for sensitivity testing is based on the method outlined by Guevara (2005). The extract's acute cutaneous toxicity/sensitivity was tested by applying an ointment containing *acapulco*, and *santol* extracts at the highest concentrations of 5% (w/w) to the albino rats' shaved backs.

Development of Formulation Guide

A formulation guide was crafted to feature step-by-step protocols for extract preparation, ointment formulation and safety guidelines for storage and application.

Treatment of Data

Both descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were employed. All experimental measurements were carried out in triplicate. and were expressed as an average of three analyses. Zones of inhibition was determined and recorded. Standard ranges were utilized to evaluate the physical characteristics of the formulated ointment.

Ethical Considerations

This study was approved by Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) at Saint Mary's University, Ponce Street, DMM, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, with cellphone number: 09177053041 and email: reb@smu.edu.ph. The reference number is SMUREB code 20240680.

III. Results and Discussions

Section 1. Antimicrobial Activity of Plant Samples

Table 1.
Santol Leaf Crude Extract (SLCE)

	ZONES OF INHIBITION		
	Concentrations		
	250 mg/ml	500 mg/ml	750 mg/ml
Staphylococcus aureus			
Positive Control	21.5	21.2	22.05
Negative Control	0	0	0
Santol LCE	10.05	10.82	10.91 Partially active
Pseudomonas aeruginosa			
Positive Control	33.9	35.1	35.2
Negative Control	0	0	0
Santol LCE	12.86	14.2	14.23 Active
Candida albicans			
Positive Control	20.1	22.3	21
Negative Control	0	0	0
Santol LCE	9.2	10.93	11.63 Partially active

Guevarra et al 2005 (<10mm-inactive; 10-13mm-partially active; 14-19- active; >19mm-very active)

The antimicrobial evaluation of Santol Leaf Crude Extract (SLCE) demonstrates varying degrees of inhibitory activity against both bacterial and fungal pathogens. Zones of inhibition (ZOI) data show how SLCE's effectiveness differs across organism types and concentrations, giving insights into its potential as a natural antimicrobial agent.

Antibacterial Activity Against Staphylococcus aureus. SLCE exhibited *partially active* inhibition against *S. aureus*, a Gram-positive bacterium. The ZOIs increased slightly with concentration. While there is a slight increase, the change is not significantly dose-dependent, and all ZOIs remain relatively active compared to the positive control, 21.2–22.05 mm. This suggests SLCE has limited but measurable antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, though its potency appears to plateau beyond 500 mg/ml.

Antibacterial Activity Against Pseudomonas aeruginosa. Interestingly, SLCE showed *active* and *better* inhibition against *P. aeruginosa*, a Gram-negative bacteria, with a more notable increase in ZOIs. Though still far from the positive control values, 33.9–35.2 mm, the extract displays better potency against this Gram-negative pathogen than it did against *S. aureus*. This is notable because *P. aeruginosa* is typically harder to inhibit due to its tough outer membrane and resistance mechanisms. The data suggest that SLCE may contain compounds capable of breaching or interfering with *P. aeruginosa*'s defense systems.

Antifungal Activity Against Candida albicans. Against *C. albicans*, SLCE displayed *partially active* antifungal activity, with increasing ZOIs as the concentration increased. While the inhibition zones are clearly present, they remain significantly smaller than those of the positive controls. This

indicates that while SLCE has some antifungal potential, it is less potent than standard antifungal agents and may require higher concentrations or formulation adjustments to enhance its efficacy.

The negative controls showed no inhibition in all concentrations, affirming that the solvent used in the crude extract did not contribute to any antimicrobial activity. The positive controls consistently produced large zones of inhibition, confirming the accuracy and responsiveness of the test organisms and validating the experimental setup.

All in all, the results suggest that Santol Leaves Crude Extract (SLCE) exhibits antimicrobial activity, though its potency is relatively *partially active* to *active* in all tested organisms. Notably, its most significant inhibitory effect was observed against *P. aeruginosa*, which is encouraging given the pathogen's inherent resistance. Its activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans* was present but considerably weaker and showed only minor increases with higher concentrations. The antimicrobial results had been performed and validated by a Biologists, Registered Medical Technologist and a Registered Pharmacist.

Table 2
Zone of Inhibition of Acapulco Leaves Crude Extract (ALCE)

ZONES OF INHIBITION			
	Concentrations		
	250 mg/ml	500 mg/ml	750 mg/ml
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>			
<i>Positive Control</i>	28.6	21.9	27.2
<i>Negative Control</i>	0	0	0
<i>Andadasi LCE</i>	10.56	16.6	18.66 active
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>			
<i>Positive Control</i>	33.4	32.8	34.0
<i>Negative Control</i>	0	0	0
<i>Andadasi LCE</i>	8.66	9.66	12.1 Partially active
<i>Candida albicans</i>			
<i>Positive Control</i>	22.1	22.7	22.2
<i>Negative Control</i>	0	0	0
<i>Andadasi LCE</i>	18.73	19.93	21.53 Very active

Guevarra et al 2005(<10mm-inactive; 10-13mm-partially active; 14-19- active; >19mm-very active)

The results above reveal that Acapulco Leaf Crude Extracts possesses varying degrees of antimicrobial efficacy depending on the organism and extract concentration.

Antibacterial Activity Against *Staphylococcus aureus*. ALCE exhibited *active* inhibition against *S. aureus*, a Gram-positive bacterium. The ZOIs increased slightly with concentration. While these zones are smaller than those produced by the positive control, the results demonstrate that ALCE has notable inhibitory activity against *S. aureus*. The steady increase in ZOI with concentration suggests that higher doses of the extract may improve its antibacterial efficacy.

Antibacterial Activity Against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. ALCE showed *partially active* against *P. aeruginosa*, a Gram-negative bacterium. In contrast, the positive control maintained significantly larger ZOIs across all concentrations. While the activity is relatively low, the gradual increase still

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suggests a degree of potency. This lower sensitivity may be attributed to the outer membrane barrier and efflux mechanisms typically found in Gram-negative bacteria, which can impede the action of plant-derived compounds (<https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics12081304>).

Antifungal Activity Against *Candida albicans*. Among the tested organisms, *C. albicans* showed very active, which is the most promising response to ALCE. The ZOIs for ALCE ranged from 18.73 mm to 21.53 mm, which is interpreted as very active, approaching those of the positive control (22.1–22.7 mm). This suggests a strong antifungal potential of Acapulco leaf extract, especially at higher concentrations. The results imply that the active phytochemicals in ALCE might be particularly effective against fungal pathogens, possibly by disrupting cell membrane integrity or interfering with fungal metabolism.

The negative control showed no zones of inhibition, confirming the absence of antimicrobial effects in the solvent used. The positive controls performed consistently well, validating the sensitivity of the test organisms and the reliability of the experimental setup.

Overall, ALCE demonstrated antimicrobial activity, with the most significant inhibition observed against *Candida albicans*, followed by *Staphylococcus aureus*, and the least against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. These findings support the traditional use of Acapulco leaves in treating skin infections and suggest that it holds potential for development into natural antimicrobial agents, particularly for fungal and Gram-positive bacterial infections.

Section 2. Formulation of Antimicrobial Ointment Utilizing the Most Potent Leaf Extracts Concentration.

Figure 2
Formulated Topical Ointment

Two antimicrobial ointments were formulated using *santol* and *andadasi* plant extracts at a concentration of 750 mg/mL, as identified to be the most potent based on antimicrobial evaluation tests. This concentration exhibited superior inhibitory activity against clinically selected skin microorganisms. The final formulations were stable, well-tolerated, and suitable for topical application.

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Section 3. Physical Properties of Formulated Antimicrobial Topical Ointment

Table 3
Physical Characteristics

PARAMETERS					
	Color	Odor	Consistency	pH	Spreadability
Santol Ointment	Dark green	Plant-infused coconut scent	Smooth, semi-solid	5.1	Easily spreadable
Andadasi Ointment	Dark green	Herbal-coconut scent	Smooth, semi-solid	6.6	Smooth application

Typical range: 4.5 to 6.5. (It means, skin-friendly, matching the natural pH of human skin (around 5.5).)

The formulated topical ointment exhibited desirable physical characteristics and conformed to established quality standards, indicating suitability for topical application. The formulation and evaluation of physical characteristics were evaluated by two Registered Pharmacists.

Section 4. Safety Profile of the Formulated Antimicrobial Ointment

Figure 3
Non-Irritancy Test

The non-irritancy of the formulated antimicrobial topical ointment was confirmed through a skin irritation test, with no signs of erythema or edema, indicating that the formulated ointment is non-irritating and well-tolerated.

Table 4
Scratch and Patch Test

Time Interval	Santol Ointment	Acapulco Ointment
24 hours	No edema	No edema
48 hours	No edema	No edema
72 hours	No edema	No edema

Based on the patch and scratch test results, the formulation showed an absence of edema confirming its safety for topical application

Section 5. Formulation Guide: Home-Based Antimicrobial Topical Ointment

Below is a formulation guide for a topical antimicrobial ointment suitable for minor cuts, skin irritations, or preventive care using herbal or plant extracts known for their antimicrobial potency.

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This guide provides a basic formulation for a topical antimicrobial ointment that can be easily made at home. Ingredients can be adjusted based on personal needs and preferences. The development of this formulation guide involved a a Biologist, Registered Medical Technologist and two (2) Registered Pharmacists.

Ingredients (for 100 g batch):

Ingredients	Amount	Function
White petrolatum (Vaseline)	85 g	Ointment base, occlusive agent
Coconut oil	10 g	Emollient, mild antimicrobial
Plant Extract	85g	antimicrobial
Optional: Lavender oil	0.5 g (0.5%)	Soothing, antimicrobial fragrance

Materials Needed:

- bowl or double boiler
- Measuring spoons or digital scale
- Stirring rod or spoon
- Clean jars or tins for storage
- Gloves and clean workspace (for hygiene)

Step by Step Preparation

1. Collection of Mature leaves.
2. Shade drying or air drying. The collected leaves will be placed in a mesh net to ensure even drying. This process effectively reduces their moisture content, helping to prevent and inhibit the growth of harmful microorganisms.
3. Garbling. This involves the removal of extraneous materials such as dirt, debris and other adulterants to ensure the purity and quality of the product.
4. Milling or grinding. This step involves reducing the size of the dried leaves using a blender or mortar and pestle to enhance their dispersibility.
5. Melt the base. Gently heat petrolatum and coconut oil together using a double boiler. Stir until fully melted and uniform.
6. Cool slightly. Let the mixture cool down.
7. Add active ingredients or scent (Optional)
8. Ointment Preparation. An ointment formulation of 85% will be prepared by adding 85 g of the leaves powder to 100g of petroleum. The ointment formulation will be mixed until a homogenous mixture is obtained.
9. Pour into jars. Transfer to small clean jars or tins while still soft. Let it cool and solidify at room temperature.
10. Label and store. Label the container with ingredients and date. Store in a cool, dry place for up to 1 months

This guide provides a basic formulation for a topical antimicrobial ointment that can be easily made at home. Adjust ingredients based on personal needs and preferences!

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Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusion

This study successfully formulated and evaluated a topical antimicrobial ointment derived from ethanolic leaf extracts of *Sandoricum koetjape* (Santol) and *Cassia alata* (Andadasi), targeting clinically relevant skin pathogens. The antimicrobial screening confirmed that both plant extracts exhibit varying degrees of inhibitory activity, with *Santol* extract showing the strongest effect against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, while *Andadasi* extract demonstrated the most notable activity against *Candida albicans*. Based on the antimicrobial results, a concentration of 750 mg/mL was selected as the most potent for both plant extracts. The formulated ointments displayed favorable physical characteristics, including smooth semi-solid consistency, acceptable pH within the skin-friendly range (4.5–6.5), and excellent spreadability. Organoleptic properties such as color and scent were consistent with herbal-based products and aligned well with user expectations for natural formulations. Safety assessment through scratch and patch test confirmed the absence of edema over a 72-hour period, indicating that the formulations are non-irritating and safe for topical use. Overall, this study supports the potential of *Sandoricum koetjape* and *Cassia alata* leaf extracts as natural sources of antimicrobial agents for topical applications. The developed ointments offer a promising alternative to conventional treatments for minor skin infections, with the added benefits of plant-based actives and minimal formulation complexity. Furthermore, a step-by-step guide for extraction and formulation has been developed, enabling reproducibility and potential scale-up for broader use in community or clinical settings.

Recommendations

1. Scale-up the findings for broader use in community or clinical settings. To consider developing educational materials or community outreach programs to raise awareness of the benefits and proper usage of herbal-based topical treatments, especially in rural or resource-limited areas.
2. While in vitro results are promising, in vivo studies on animal models or human volunteers are recommended to assess the ointment's efficacy, pharmacokinetics, and long-term safety under real-world conditions.
3. Conduct long-term stability testing under various storage conditions to ensure the product maintains its physical, chemical, and microbiological integrity over time.
4. Explore the incorporation of natural preservatives, antioxidants, or enhancers to further improve shelf-life, efficacy, and skin absorption.
5. Evaluate the efficacy of the ointment against a wider range of microbial strains, including resistant bacteria and emerging skin pathogens, to determine its broader therapeutic potential.
6. Initiate clinical trials to validate therapeutic claims and begin alignment with regulatory requirements for herbal or pharmaceutical product registration.

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Appendices A: Ethics Clearance

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ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

This certifies that the following protocol and related documents have been approved, monitored, and granted clearance by SMUREB.

SMUREB Code: 2024 0680

Research Proponent/s: CATHELYN C. MARIANO
MARIA SHIELA M. RAMOS
JULIET SANDERS, (External Collaborator)

Title: Converting Biological Resources into Herbal-based Ointment for Topical Application: Formulation and Efficacy Evaluation

Protocol Version No.: 1

Version Date: June 10, 2024

ICF Version No.: N/A

Version Date: N/A

Type of Review: Exempted

The research proponent has submitted the final report form and has complied with all the requirements of the Research Ethics Board.

Issued and signed on May 15, 2025.

JASON ARNOLD L. MASLANG
 Chair, SMUREB

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Second Floor, Rev. John Van Bauwel Building
SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street, Don Mariano Marcos
Bayombong, 3700 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines
www.smu.edu.ph / reb@smu.edu.ph
078-321-2221 / 09177053041

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Appendices B: Photo documentation

Collection, and oven-drying of plant samples

Extracts for antimicrobial assay

Powderization and extraction of plant samples

Antimicrobial analysis to determine the most potent concentration

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Preparation for the formulation of topical antimicrobial ointment

Ointment formulation and physical evaluation

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Scratch and patch test

Planning for the development of formulation guide. The team involved Biologist, Registered Medical Technologist and Registered Pharmacists